

The Connoisseur and the Consumer: Assessing Design Quality

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Abstract

Designers, like wine connoisseurs, rely on well-established methodologies to make subjective evaluations. David Hume laid out methods for connoisseurship in the 18th century that are used today. Such judgments involve familiarity with and passion for one's subject, forming understandings with other experts, and making finely discriminating comparisons. Subjective assessments require neutralizing interference and anticipating how a design is to be used.

Designers practice these methods both formally and informally, both at work and in hobbies such as collecting. They are an important part of the overall lifestyle of the designer. Sociologist Pierre Bourdieu has observed that connoisseurship is recognized as a key trait that distinguishes those with cultural capital from others. Designers cultivate connoisseurship, but they often design for audiences who do not cultivate connoisseurship.

Therefore, design researchers may carefully select test subjects for their ages, psychological profiles, and even incomes, yet still be biased toward those who share a sense of connoisseurship. Such subjects have the vocabulary, the methodology, and the social confidence to voice opinions about design.

When assessing design, class-based biases present serious challenges to meeting the needs of a full range of consumers.

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Designers make subjective aesthetic assessments throughout the design process. Subjective assessments are central to framing design problems and refining their solutions. Wine connoisseurs face many similar challenges when trying to assess the quality of wine. In fact we can recognize connoisseurship as a general set of methodologies for identifying the best in any aesthetic domain. But we must, at the same time, recognize that connoisseurship sets those within the design profession apart from many segments of the population. Those who make their livings through aesthetic judgment are socially isolated from those with less cultural capital and see the practice of connoisseurship as routine behavior. Even researchers who conduct focus groups or field-test designs may discount or overlook the views of those from other social groups.

Qualitative assessment of design

Designers, unlike engineers, routinely employ cultural and aesthetic considerations to frame problems, analyze needs, synthesize possible approaches, and choose optimal solutions. Many of these considerations are subjective in nature. Even design issues that seem to be objective may in fact rely on the subjective way that designers or their clients frame a design problem. (Baudrillard, 2000) Whether creating a building, an appliance, or a Web site, creative problem solving involves continually generating possibilities and then winnowing out the best. Designers are trained to focus on seemingly banal aspects of a project, such as brick color or button configurations, and develop a heightened sensitivity to that area. Once arriving at what seem to be the best possible configurations, a designer must negotiate with colleagues, clients, and focus groups, to assess what version of a design is ultimately most suitable to go into production.

Subjective judgments are problematic enough to have generated a large body of philosophical inquiry. David Hume proposed in 1757 in *Of the Standard of Taste* that such issues could be reliably evaluated by a joint verdict of true judges. (Hume, 1998) Each member of Hume's "counsel of true judges" should possess fine discrimination, familiarity with the sort of work being evaluated, and a chance to make appreciative comparisons with similar objects. Each judge must also have an understanding of the purpose of the evaluated object, and an ability to enter into the spirit of a work on its own terms. This description is not inappropriate to describe how designers, and other experts, attempt to make reliable assessments today.

But these methods have also been questioned. (Levinson, 2002; Shusterman, 1989) Indeed, it is not hard to see the weaknesses of Hume's methods when applied to design: a design is good because the designer is a tastemaker who can deem it good – but who determines that he is a tastemaker? The designer has a keen sense of taste because others with taste agree he does – but how are they qualified? The design is good because other tastemakers say it is good – but who gives authority to those tastemakers? The design is good because it is similar to work in the established "design canon" – but how was the canon assembled? We find that there is no objective ground on which to ultimately judge a work, or even identify a person who can pass such judgment.

While Hume's methods may not obtain objective truths, they achieve reliable results, and they are, in some form or fashion, employed for assessing the quality of everything from

architectural models to fine wines to car advertisements. Hume's methods *satisfice*, meaning they are a reliable way to obtain results that are, seemingly, good enough.

The characteristics and methodologies of connoisseurs are basically the same as those of Hume's judges. A connoisseur is serious and involved with his subject, yet possesses a passion for the subject on its own terms, unclouded by mundane distractions. While he may be an amateur, he is no dilettante in the sense of taking his subject lightly.

Methodologies for qualitative assessment of wine

Connoisseurship applies to many different practices, including wine tastings and design competitions. Serious wine tastings involve a number of experts gathered together, not unlike Hume's "counsel of true judges." These experts are usually familiar not just with wines but also with things like grape varieties, and the arcane vocabulary of wine assessment.

The connoisseur of wine actively engages his subject, constantly exercising his powers of judgment. Wine critics defend their judgments, in part, by reporting on their vineyard visits, their methods of sampling wines, etc. (Langewiesche, 2000) While it seems obvious that wine appreciators must, first, appreciate wine, wine literature includes ridicule for investors who speculate in wine without drinking it. (Parker, 1999)

Wine tasters, like many designers, make efforts to bring as much objectivity as possible to their subjective evaluations. They focus on taste and smell, in part, by covering over labels (alas) and other identifying marks to take "blind" samples. Wine tasters reduce other distracting sensations via rinsing the mouth between samples, not wearing perfume, etc.

Hume held that the subject of assessment should be understood in terms of its ends, and some critics strongly discount wine tastings because they are so different from the way most people drink wine. They point out that ordinary people swallow wine, rather than spitting it out, and usually have it with food. (Parker, 1999)

Tastings usually offer wines within some restricted category, such as French Cabernets, so that fine comparisons can be extracted. Interestingly, it is popular in wine tastings to introduce a "ringer" into the mix – a wine of very poor quality. It is not uncommon for a

taster's senses to be fatigued by many similar wines and gravitate toward one that is different, no matter how bad. (Some may have experienced similar misjudgments in design presentations.) The ringer serves as a check against inattentive judges. But usually the ringer's obvious inferiority also serves as a basis of agreement among judges who may have diverging opinions about everything else.

While one may set any number of conditions on a "counsel of true judges," their ability to agree *most of the time* is critical. When in agreement, their judgments are, effectively, self-validating. Occasional disagreements among experts provide opportunities for debates and are a sign of engagement. From such debates, each judge can cultivate his understanding of the field through exposure to alternate points of view.

A *complete* lack of agreement, however, would cause each judge's opinion to nullify the others.⁷ More importantly, it would call into question the entire basis of their ability to judge.

A "counsel of true judges," in the subjective arena, serves as a self-validating and self-perpetuating body, which presents a dilemma. Shusterman points out that Hume's "standard of taste" serves "... normative stability rather than epistemological certainty or ontological grounding." (Shusterman, 1989) A wine critic can tell us that a wine contains hints of leather or has great astringency, but not whether we will enjoy the wine as much as he did. The convention of wine tastings establishes the idea that wine appreciation is a valid skill, that a person who enjoys a fine Cotes du Rhone has better taste (in the social sense) than a person who enjoys a cheap Muscatel.

Authority is conferred upon wine experts through wine columns in newspapers, charity wine events, etc. Authority is also conferred on the whole idea of wine expertise as something to cultivate. For those used to cultivating a sense of design, wine connoisseurship may seem normal, even natural. However for those with little opportunity to cultivate a taste for wine or anything else purely for the sake of pleasure, wine tastings may seem like a waste of time, or merely bizarre.

Design methodologies

Like wine connoisseurs, designers engage in semi-scientific assessments of the products of their field. Formal design competitions parallel wine tastings. People of stature assemble to compare entries in some category. Stature may involve educational degrees and work history, but importantly, passionate engagement with the subject.

The category of work to be judged is restrictive, such as “the best book covers of 2004.” Judges don’t have to determine that a work is ultimately or eternally beautiful, but just the best of the designs offered. Similarly, categories can be narrowed to a specific aspect of the work, such as book covers, without considering book interiors or book plot.

Typically, the names of entrants are hidden and other distractions are minimized to maximize objectivity.

Judges, looking at book covers on a table, may have little sense of what it means to shop for, or to read, a given book. Designers, as part of their jobs, routinely envision how new work will be experienced by its end consumers. But the ends of design, unlike wine, are complex and infinitely varied. It is not surprising that design competitions routinely face criticism for being superficial “beauty contests.”

In fact, many designers deny taking awards seriously. Yet like wine tastings, these awards reassure us that standards can be agreed upon and that design sensibilities can be reliably cultivated.

Like wine tastings, design competitions establish that a standard of taste can be determined for the general population. Those who establish this standard are those with cultivated sensibilities and the energy to constantly revise and refine those powers.

The designer sensibility

Design practice involves sustained effort, and spills over from the workplace to leisure activities. Collecting is one way designers practice connoisseurship in their leisure time.

Designers are known to amass everything from tribal masks to robot toys. Tibor Kalmon's onion rings, part of SFMOMA's *Tiborocity* exhibition in 1999, may be one of the best-known designer collections. Pentagram co-founder Alan Fletcher counts Henry Steiner's comprehensive collection of airline sick bags, Ronald Shakespear's baking powder tins, Arnold Schwartzman's steel record needle boxes, and Shigeo Fukuda's collection of Western plastic food, among collections of designers he knows. (Fletcher, 2001) While such collecting practices may be highly individuated, it allows designers to stay in the practice of making subjective judgments.

Sociologist Pierre Bourdieu observed that designers have enviable lifestyles, not because they are well paid, but because they are practiced at symbolic appropriation. Celebrating Kalmon's substitution of fried food for fine china, etc., is exactly that. Whether at work or leisure, designers substitute panache for luxury.

In Bourdieu's words, the designer is a "dominated member of the dominant class." Designers are not typically the best paid of "knowledge workers," but are able to maximize cultural profit at minimum economic cost. They are socially comfortable with their clients and other professionals because of their powers of discrimination, rather than because they live in luxury. Bourdieu sums up the preoccupations of this group:

Liking the same things differently, liking different things, less obviously marked out for admiration – these are some of the strategies for outflanking, overtaking and displacing which, by maintaining a permanent revolution in tastes, enable the dominated, less wealthy fractions, whose appropriations must, in the main, be exclusively symbolic, to secure exclusive possessions at every moment. (1984: 282)

When the designer is not bringing his cultural capital to workplace projects, he is securing it for himself.

My point is not that designers are social climbers. Pierre Bourdieu and Thorstein Veblen (Veblen, 1934) are well known for their characterizations of "lifestyle" activities in terms of social status. Bourdieu in particular stressed how status involves refusal of the tastes of the less wealthy or less educated. But the end goal of status seeking is not snobbish distancing from one's inferiors. It is getting along with friends, family, clients and coworkers. People enjoy being thought better than others, but they desperately do not want to be thought any

worse. In that light, Bourdieu and Veblen are mechanistic, but not cynical. Designers practice connoisseurship because they would be ashamed to do otherwise.

Connoisseurship as a generalizable skill

Connoisseurship is a skill, a habit, even an attitude. We see that design practice, often thought of as the “practical” side of fine art, in fact has much in common with wine connoisseurship, long associated with luxury and leisure. It is only a hypothesis that wine connoisseurs could easily develop a sense of design, but we are all familiar with how designers apply connoisseurship to other domains, such as collecting.

Bourdieu observed that an “aesthetic disposition” was a prerequisite to membership in upper-middle-class society, and describes how a cultivated person brings skills to any task. “This transposable disposition, armed with a set of perceptual and evaluative schemes that are available for general application, inclines its owner towards other cultural experiences and enables him to perceive, classify, and memorize them differently.” (Bourdieu, 1984)

Designers earn a place on a counsel of true judges, not through possession of luxury goods, but through the constant exercise of cultivated sensibilities. Even as the public’s tastes grow more refined, designers stay ahead of the “permanent revolution” of popular tastes by applying connoisseurship to all aspects of life. The designer habitually employs informed tastes rather than passively consuming goods. The movies the designer sees must be more than merely entertaining; wines more than intoxicating; food more than filling; chairs more than comfortable. All are arenas for employing cultivated sensibilities.

Sociologist Douglas Holt contrasts the lifestyles of Americans with the most and the least cultural capital. (Holt, 1998) He surveyed people in terms of their income, their education, and their parents’ income and education. Holt noted that people with little cultural capital characterized their furniture, their hobbies, and their leisure activities in terms of fitting in with established genres. For instance, many referred to their furniture as “country” or “Victorian,” rather than in terms of individuated, eclectic choices as the more affluent subjects did. Holt observed how those who saw themselves as culturally marginal sought to solidify their identity within mass culture via participation in it. In contrast, those with the most cultural capital sought a sense of identity apart from mass culture, via their critical and

conditional acceptance of mass-produced goods. In Holt's observation, the connoisseur is not intimidated by the larger culture, and can enjoy the luxury of setting conditions upon his participation in that culture. This is an altogether different way of understanding class-based consumer cultures than "rich people like opera," etc.

User research

Many designers are keenly aware of the cultural distance between themselves and the consumers for whom they produce work. For just this reason, designers conduct research on members of the general population, from whom they elicit opinions about their designs. But, in fact, field research shares significant features with wine tastings and design competitions.

Generally, researchers recruit people of specific ages, sexes, incomes and education levels to represent a design project's potential audience. These research subjects might also be chosen for their specific behaviors such as "uses mass transit daily," or by psychological characteristics, such as "optimistic but introverted."

Unlike Hume's counsel of true judges, these consumers' singular qualification to evaluate work may be their actual, rather than theoretical, use for the product. A research subject may need widgets or use widgets, and hence be able to form opinions that a widget designer would not. But often subjects are asked to enter into the spirit of needing or wanting widgets, then given a variety of widgets to compare, and asked which widget they consider the best. Researchers may ask subjects to assess subtle distinctions among different versions of widgets, or to categorize widgets in various fashions. Researchers may ask subjects to associate words with the widgets or relate how widgets might fit into their lifestyles. Subjects may be asked to rank widgets and explain why they made such rankings. Average people are asked, during a research session, to become connoisseurs of widgets.

Some subjects will lack the vocabulary to express their feelings. Some will not be in the habit of abstract thought that is required for such tasks. Some will lack confidence in their opinions. Some will have nagging thoughts that, within their culture of scarcity, theoretical widgets are not worth evaluating. Bourdieu's analysis of Frenchmen transcends French culture: he observed that people want to fit into a social class. Fitting into a social class demands ongoing conformity to the morés of that class. Getting along in a culture of poverty

demands not “putting on airs,” such as acting like a connoisseur.

A surprising problem for researchers is that a limited set of research subjects will, in fact, rise eagerly to the task of connoisseurship. These may not be the most affluent subjects, but they will be those with some cultural capital. The person of reduced circumstances – the bohemian, the drug addict, the widow – will have greater influence than others in their supposed demographic. Likewise, the newly affluent – the migrant worker who married well, the small farmer who sold his land for a good profit – may defer to more confident cohorts or elect not to participate, figuring they’d have little to contribute.

Holt interviewed subjects at the extremes of class in the United States. He recounted the remarks of a woman who had become affluent, but lacked the family training or formal education to behave as a member of the upper class. Although she had been acquiring antique furniture, she could not explain her preferences in this area. Eventually both she and the interviewer became embarrassed by his persistent questions and her continued inability to state her interests in the furniture beyond “just liking” it. (Holt, 1998)

Holt also noted how subjects with a high degree of cultural capital provided him with lengthy discussions on the merits and demerits of objects within any category mentioned. Holt even speculated as to whether these individuals acquired objects just so they could discuss the merits of such goods. Holt noted that “For [those with a high degree of cultural capital] the interview itself was clearly an enjoyable experience since it closely paralleled this [evaluative] style of consuming.”

When conducting field studies, a researcher has reason to be doubly biased toward responses from cultivated subjects: not only would a connoisseur speak confidently, and with a richer vocabulary, than other subjects, he would also be likely to speak the researcher’s own language and see things more from the researcher’s own point of view.

From self-validation to outreach

Designers are challenged to establish standards for subjective evaluations. But designers are also challenged to depart from the standards of their own social group. If designers only talk to themselves, or only to people like themselves, they become irrelevant to others. Rather

than adopt this or that new research technique, designers may need to consider how they define themselves socially. Rather than pin hopes on a style or design technique that will “speak to everyone,” designers may need to learn to listen to those who speak differently. Rather than dismissing those with “dreadful” taste, designers can discover how various tastes make sense within different cultures.

Finally, designers may have to accept that the gap between cultivated and uncultivated tastes cannot be addressed apart from the social and political issues of poverty and class isolation in general. (Wilk, 1999)

Conclusions

Designers may gain insights into their own methods of assessment by recognizing themselves as connoisseurs. In particular, they may see the connoisseur’s tendency toward self-validation as pervasive and problematic. This is of particular concern in the way connoisseurship can reinforce class-based aesthetic positions.

Designers can research how various populations receive their work, but should take care to not expect connoisseur-style input from all research subjects. Researchers may need to go to great lengths to get feedback from people who are inarticulate, or lack confidence in their own opinions. Generally, designers can develop better appreciation for people with design tastes unlike their own through contact with people from different cultural groups.

Design sensibilities grow out of deep places within communities, within classes, and within whole cultures. (hooks, 1995) Designers might beneficially cultivate their tastes for the people who generate such cultures.

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